
CLLOUD-BASED PROJECT MANAGEMENT MODELS FOR NEW-ICT PROJECTS: AN IN-DEPTH INVESTIGATION

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ABSTRACT

Modern organisations have found cloud-based project management to be a great tool for productive collaboration and progress tracking. Cloud computing provides an accessible and versatile platform for efficient project management, which is especially useful with distributed teams and remote work becoming the norm. In this paper, we'll look at how cloud-based project management tools and processes can improve team collaboration, communication, and real-time progress monitoring. The distributed nature of many SW development organisations makes management a challenge. The cloud is quickly becoming a viable option in this context. Also, by incorporating new information and communication technologies into old management practices, project management is sloppy. In order to administer New-ICT services in a Cloud Computing environment, the thesis suggests a user-friendly integrated management system that unifies the activities of different projects. With this method consolidating data and information from various projects into one, project management is predicted to increase management efficiency when used to new information and communication technology service projects. This technique is based on software as a service (SaaS) cloud computing.

Keywords: Cloud computing, ICT Projects, Software (SW) development

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INTRODUCTION

Project management that is both effective and efficient is crucial for organisations to succeed in today's fast-paced commercial world. Conventional methods of project management are encountering new difficulties in keeping up with the proliferation of remote work and distributed teams. One game-changing option is cloud-based project management, which uses the resources of the cloud to improve teamwork, communication, and real-time tracking of project status [1]. Over the course of several centuries, project management has become an international phenomenon. Whether it's constructing one of the Seven Wonders of the World or developing an app for the cloud, effective project management is becoming more than just a badge of honour; it's a need. There needs to be a way to manage projects, whether it's a tiny company, a decentralised workforce, or a global brand. At the beginning of a project, every driven entrepreneur dreams of great success. Following a project from inception to completion is an arduous task. The common understanding of project management software is that it is a tool for organising and coordinating the various activities needed to complete a project in a timely manner while still meeting all of the predetermined goals [2].

Between the years 1900 and 1950, the idea of modern project management began to take shape. During this time, the project timeline was compressed due to technological advancements. The mobility and efficient distribution of resources were made possible by automobiles. Communicating became much quicker with the advent of telecommunications networks. Both the job description and Henry Gantt's Gantt chart saw extensive use. Project management software has limitless advantages. The traditional trinity of paper, pencil, and strategy/methodology stood for project management software in the past. Nevertheless, technology advances with the passage of time. Project management software is primarily used for tasks such as scheduling, allocating resources, and planning. If businesses want to be as competitive as possible and stand out from the competition, project management software is a crucial tool [3].

Cloud System

Traditional IT	IaaS	Paas	SaaS
Applications	Applications	Applications	Applications
Runtimes	Runtimes	Runtimes	Runtimes
Security & Integration	Security & Integration	Security & Integration	Security & Integration
Databases	Databases	Databases	Databases
Servers	Servers	Servers	Servers
Virtualization	Virtualization	Virtualization	Virtualization
Server HW	Server HW	Server HW	Server HW
Storage	Storage	Storage	Storage
Networking	Networking	Networking	Networking
User Manage		Managed by Vendor	

Figure 1: Cloud Services

Comprehending cloud computing is necessary in order to familiarise oneself with cloud. Cloud computing can be defined in a number of different ways, based on the perspectives of academics, designers, engineers, developers, managers, clients, and other individuals. On-demand, utility, virtualisation resource pool, online services, and professional vision are some of the terms that can be used to summarise these concepts [4]. Figure 1 depicts the Cloud Service Type that is being discussed.

Overview

The details of the project, the allocation of resources, the client, and the skill-set requirements can all be managed with the assistance of this program, which helps to keep track of everything and prevents things from spiralling out of hand. There are two different levels of users who are able to access the application: the manager and the resource. To alter the project details, such as the name of the project and the duration of the project, to add or remove clients from the project, to add skills that are required for the project, to assign or remove resources from the project, and to cancel the project, the manager is the only person who has the power to make these changes. It is possible to assign resources to a project by taking into consideration both the skill set that has been possessed by the resource in question and the skills that are required by the project. When a management does this, it is much simpler for them to determine which resource is appropriate for a project based on the talents that are required by the project. In addition, managers have the option to access information about the resources, such as the names of the resources, the availability of the resources, the years of experience of the resources, and the resumes of the resources, as well as remove or add projects to the resource. When it comes to clients, managers have the ability to add or remove clients from a project (with only one client per project), update the name of the client, toggle the client status between active and inactive, and remove the client from the project. When it comes to the skill-set, managers have the ability to add a new talent, update current skills, approve or reject skill requests from resources, and delete a skill among other options.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The purpose of this study was to investigate a number of different concepts as well as the issues that naturally occur in a variety of cloud computing settings. Several various cloud computing delivery models have been examined, one of which is Software as a Service (SaaS), which provides clients with the ability to access the infrastructure of the provider through a user interface. An other delivery model that has been discussed for the infrastructure is one in which customers have access to fundamental computing capabilities provided by the service provider. The platform as a service model, which offers platform development as a service, is the last delivery model that was investigated in this study based on its characteristics. It is worth noting that the study has also investigated the security issue as an additional thought that is concerning [5].

In [6], the author presents a solution for multiple criteria decision-making (MCDM) that is both integrated and cost-effective. This solution is intended for cloud service evaluation and system selection. It gives decision-makers the ability to compare cloud services based on quality of service criteria. A more thorough distance measuring algorithm that is based on cloud droplet distribution has been presented. This is particularly relevant in light of the fact that typical cloud models do not include differential measurement. In order to determine the grey correlation coefficient and the degree of similarity between cloud images, a new distance measurement algorithm was utilised. The calculation of the degree of similarity between the expert rating cloud model and the arithmetic mean cloud model is what is used to determine the dynamic skill weights. Next, the authors propose an ideal solution similarity technique for order of preference by similarity to ideal solution (TOPSIS) that is enhanced with grey relational

analysis (GRA). The purpose of this technique is to determine the relative proximity of positive and negative ideal solution alternatives and to construct multiple optimisation models. When determining the significance of the circumstance, the relative proximity of all of the available possibilities is taken into consideration.

The objective of [7] was to determine which software would be most suitable for the implementation of a cloud computing system for the newly established faculty of science and technology which is located at Tehran University. When it comes to the implementation of a cloud computing system, the first step is to collect suitable criteria from the relevant literature and then define them with the assistance of experienced experts. Following this, the criteria are weighted, and the alternatives are prioritised by employing the intuitive combinative distance-based assessment (CODAS) multi-attribute choice approach that makes use of category values. Taking into consideration the findings, it is clear that the open-stack cloud computing system is the most suitable alternative.

Concerning smart grid privacy, the authors of [8] investigate optimal energy management concerns, such as distribution of energy on the supply side and responsiveness of the supply to distributed energy. First, they offered the idea of smart grids powered by cloud computing and framed the optimal energy management problem as one of maximising society welfare with net revenue and consumer net income. The goal of the application container virtualisation technology described in reference [9] was to provide a micro-service framework-based integrated platform for managing resources. Internet of Things (IoT) cloud applications can be easily built and deployed on this platform. Having said that, the micro-service model has not been definitively defined. A new tool service for developing and releasing Internet of Things (IoT) cloud apps has been developed. Through invocation connections, developers can create sets of service functionalities by combining services.

Virtualisation technology and application capabilities have not been thoroughly investigated in relation to performance trade-offs, despite the fact that edge computing resources substantially affect end-to-end performance. The authors of [10] used numerous web service implementations, container architectures, and uni-kernels to analyse the performance dynamics of alternative cloud computing technologies. A conceptual platform for orchestrating cloud services at the edge and its basic design principles were inspired by the testing findings. In an edge cloud, several virtual components are mixed according to performance needs or capabilities.

A reversible Bloom filter is the basis of the efficient fine-grained uncorrelated data mining approach proposed in [11]. If the cloud server does not act in good faith while processing or deleting data and fails to provide pertinent proof, as mentioned by the authors, the user will likely be able to promptly detect its malicious behaviour. In order to prove that the suggested system is safe and useful, the writers give extensive performance and security analyses and estimations. An integrated scientific cloud structure, science gateway cloud, was created and put into action by the writers of [12]. To facilitate the efficient processing of diverse scientific applications on heterogeneous cloud resources, this framework acts as a mediator between users and suppliers. In particular, we develop performance-unimpaired cost-optimized resource management methods by analysing the long-term payment plans of cloud resource providers. The authors conclude by demonstrating, using a variety of modelling and experimental results, that the suggested system significantly surpasses conventional cloud systems.

The authors present a safe mitigation approach that allows users to establish their own access levels [13]. One way to maximise de-duplication without sacrificing user security and privacy is to provide cloud service providers the authority to authorise access to data on behalf of data owners. Our trusted safe redaction technology protects sensitive information and maintains the validity of tags by thwarting brute-force assaults, according to thorough security testing. And

in terms of computing, communication, storage costs, and reduced efficiency, our system beats competing schemes, according to thorough simulations. Attacking the deep neural network with malicious examples can cause it to malfunction. To illustrate how a model might be adversarial, consider a data set that has had a tiny bit of noise added to it. This noise would not be seen by humans, but the model would incorrectly classify it. In 2014, the research of opposing paradigms was presented and numerous attack and defence tactics were examined (ref. [14]). Deepfool, JSMA, FGSM, iterative FGSM, and jacobian-based saliency map assault are some of the developed algorithms used for adversarial example classification. Images, text fields, and intrusion detection fields all have competing training approaches, which Carlini [15] and Wagner [16] looked into. An approach to improve resilience in the face of competing text samples was put out by Li and Qiu [17].

The research proposed a method to circumvent the photo caption model's security measures by utilising deep neural networks [18,19] with three distinct trigger configurations. There was an analysis of the attack success rate and error rate of the original sample for each trigger size in the backdoor sample. The experimental results show that the original sample had an average error rate of 9.65% and the backdoor sample had an average attack success rate of 96.67% when the trigger size is 4%, regardless of the kind of trigger [20]. Cloud server failure prediction was the focus of this study, which also sought to test the authors' premise that using several system indicators would improve failure prediction. Our data acquired from one hundred cloud servers is the basis for this paper's data analysis, correlation study, and experimental results, all of which aim to provide full support for the hypothesis. Using integrated measurements as an example, the authors demonstrated their competitive advantage [21].

The results of the study of the business process life cycle showed that only 17.6% of the studied works that dealt with risk assessment included it in the cycle [22]. The findings of the domain applicability evaluation showed that 53 percent of the works that were tested were put to the test in real-time, validated, and then reused. Results for using an existing risk analysis technique in security risk analysis were positive, according to the research [23]. For the most reliable and recoverable storage solution, the proposed architecture combines the benefits of replication and erasure coding in a hybrid fashion. The real results show that the proposed hybrid architecture has a major impact on the efficiency of cloud storage [24]. Businesses are hesitant to use cloud services due to the complexity of data protection and security. To solve this issue, we provide the Triple Data Encryption Standard approach, which uses healthcare data to secure massive data in the cloud [25].

One of the numerous benefits of cloud computing is the accessibility it provides through its three service models: infrastructure as a service (IaaS), platform as a service (PaaS), and software as a service (SaaS). In addition to meeting consumer expectations and providing a number of optional extras, it provides top-notch service. The best part is that it employs a pay-per-usage model, which means there are no hidden fees when you increase or decrease the amount you pay for. Great benefits accrue to both suppliers and users, creating a win-win situation. We compared Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS) with Platform as a Service (PaaS) and found that, although both are great, PaaS is more popular with consumers [26].

This study addresses the cloud platform's data security challenge by utilising the Chaotic Fuzzy Encryption (CFE) technology and the Greedy Chemical Reaction Optimisation (GCRO) algorithm. In the offloading scenario, data is encrypted using the chaotic fuzzy approach before being sent to the cloud. With a time savings of 20% for uploading files, 15% for downloading files, 16.66% for encrypting and decrypting files, and 6.25% overall, the suggested CFE-GCRO algorithm outperforms state-of-the-art algorithms like Proxy Re-Encryption (PRE) and the Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) [27].

METHODOLOGY

New-ICT Management Triangle

The New-ICT management triangle is shown in Figure 2. What we call "Scope," "Schedule," and "Cost" in conventional project management form the left triangle. Affix "Scope" and plan "Cost" and "Schedule" in the left triangle. However, modify the 'Schedule' and reevaluate the 'Scope' priorities in case the requirements alter.

Figure 2: New-ICT Management Triangle

New-ICT

The "Schedule" in project management is set in stone, whereas the "Scope" is open to change. A fixed restriction is time. Customer Value, Quality (necessary to provide ongoing customer value), and Constraints are the elements that are measured. Although limitations are still a major consideration, they do not constitute the project's end objective. Aiming for value and adjusting restrictions to meet consumer value are two different things.

The following [Table 1] is New-ICT Triangle

Table 1: New-ICT Triangle

Goal	Descriptions
Value goal	▪ Build a releasable product
Quality goal	▪ Build a reliable, adaptable product
Constraint goal	▪ Achieve value and quality goals within acceptable constraints

New-ICT Management Life Cycle

In order to make project management easier, this research proposes a lifecycle model for managing new information and communication technology projects. Takes use of the terms "Sprint" and "Milestone" to describe discrete units of work in the context of project management, for instance. A small new solution can be developed using the Pure Repeat Life Cycle Model, a medium-sized solution can be developed using the Hybrid Repeat Life Cycle Model, and a large next-generation project can be developed using the Waterfall Repeat Life Cycle Model. These three models make up the proposed project management life cycle model. Task management, the SW life cycle, and milestones (or sprints) are the components that make up project management decisions.

Pure Repeat Life Cycle

Figure 3 shows the life cycle of a pure repetition.

Figure 3: Pure Repeat Life Cycle

The Pure Repeat Life Cycle Model is well-suited to the creation of innovative, low-risk, high-functioning solutions.

Hybrid Repeat Life Cycle

The Hybrid Repeat Life Cycle Model, as shown in Figure 4, is an appropriate framework for the development of verified operational systems. Over half of the needs for routine and anticipated functional changes

Figure 4: Hybrid Repeat Life Cycle

The Relation between New-ICT Life Cycle and SW Development Project

The paper proposes a model for project management that integrates the New-ICT methodology with the Life Cycle Model to clarify the connection between programs and projects. Project management entails various facets. To build a Top Down project by using the project-phase correlation as a model for managing tasks and sprints. There are various projects and sprints that it can generate. Figure 5 below illustrates the connection between the New-Life Cycle and the SW development project.

Figure 5: Relationship between New-ICT Life Cycle and SW development project

There are numerous projects in a single program, and each project might produce multiple sprints. A sprint consists of numerous tasks, and each task encompasses numerous procedures. Users may easily communicate project status updates and report, receive, and address issues

that arise during project execution. Additionally, it facilitates the process and allows for quick judgements in response to fluctuating requirements.

RESULTS AND STUDY

Figure 6 shows the screen for requirements management systems and functions. workflow, which encompasses the methodical management of tasks, their registration and output, export and import, template delivery, and demand tracking.

Agile Work List (65)

Sub-System	Agile Link Tar	Job Name	Agile Wo	Priority	Story Po
Agile Type of Work To assign a group, drag and drop the column name here.					
Bug					
Pure-Agile Dev.(DevOps Link)		Op. Server Manager Account Escalation a	Closed	Highest	
Story					
Pure-Agile Dev.(DevOps Link)	PMS OP. / Dev.	Agile PMS-Agile Check List Liked to Relea	Closed	High	5
Pure-Agile Dev.(DevOps Link)	PMS OP. / Dev.	Modify the Agile Project Dashboard UI	Closed	Medium	1
Pure-Agile Dev.(DevOps Link)	PMS OP. / Dev.	Agile Configuration Management -Progr	Closed	Medium	1
Pure-Agile Dev.(DevOps Link)	PMS OP. / Dev.	Application of Grid Individual Cache in Ta	Closed	Medium	0
Pure-Agile Dev.(DevOps Link)	PMS OP. / Dev.	Schedule Management(WBS Lookup)-Sta	Closed	Medium	1
Pure-Agile Dev.(DevOps Link)	PMS OP. / Dev.	Manage Agile Settings-Agile Linkage Ma	Closed	Medium	2
Pure-Agile Dev.(DevOps Link)	PMS OP. / Dev.	Schedule Management(WBS Lookup)-Ag	Closed	Medium	1
Pure-Agile Dev.(DevOps Link)	PMS OP. / Dev.	Manage Agile Settings-Improve Collabor	Closed	Medium	3
Pure-Agile Dev.(DevOps Link)	PMS OP. / Dev.	Schedule Management(WBS Lookup)- W	Closed	Medium	3
Pure-Agile Dev.(DevOps Link)	PMS OP. / Dev.	SKT SOC-> mpms Data Migration Develo	Closed	Medium	20
Pure-Agile Dev.(DevOps Link)	PMS OP. / Dev.	Scheduling(Start)-Checking Duplicate Co	Closed	Medium	1

Figure 6: requirement registration and managing

Figure 7 is a screen that may be set to run at specific intervals according to your schedule.

Progress Rate List

Project/ SubSystem	Manager	Weight	Last Week 17.10.13.(Fri)				Last Week 17.10.13.(Fri)				Next Wee
			Plan	Result	Achieve Rate	Difference	Plan	Result	Achieve Rate	Difference	
AgilePMS Dev/Imp	pms	100.00%	46.16%	36.83%	79.78%	-9.33%	49.61%	36.90%	74.39%	-12.71%	52.94%
Pure-Agile Dev	pms	30.00%	62.22%	64.75%	104.07%	2.53%	65.00%	65.00%	100.00%	0.00%	68.57%
Hybrid-Agile Dev	pms	30.00%	39.25%	23.00%	58.60%	-16.25%	43.31%	23.00%	53.11%	-20.31%	47.38%
Waterfall-Agile Dev	pms	30.00%	44.75%	31.00%	69.27%	-13.75%	48.19%	31.00%	64.33%	-17.19%	51.63%
Project Mgmt.	pms	5.00%	45.95%	24.08%	52.40%	-21.87%	53.24%	24.08%	45.23%	-29.16%	53.24%

Figure 7: Project integration Progress Management

The project integration dashboard is shown in Figure 8. As a result of giving real-time information and integrated management, DashBoard is able to manage risks and progress.

Figure 8: Project integration Dash Board

Dash Board for Velocity and Estimating is shown in Figure 9. In order to determine the extent of the demand (Story) taking into account its complexity, risk, and size, the number that is used is called the story point. In order to determine the amount of work that was completed throughout the project time, the total number of backlog story points that were completed during the sprint phase is added together.

Figure 9: Velocity & Estimating Dashboard.

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

In order to address the current issues, we have employed the Hybrid SW creation process, which combines the best features of both the classic and NEW-ICT SW development methods. Before the Hybrid SW development process can be finalised, it is necessary to alter the development culture, even if the process is critical for the project's actual implementation. Conventional service environments and procedures are still used for managing and operating most development projects at the moment. Reduced system interoperability is a direct result of the lack of structure in the organization's models and tools. Therefore, I'm providing a cloud-based integrated management system to facilitate heterogeneous data sharing in line with the management model and processes suitable for the forthcoming New-ICT deployment era. With the suggested models, you may use a plethora of external services and development platforms, and you can also synchronise your development efforts with an indefinitely offered testing and staging server. Ongoing research is essential for ensuring future security and usability. There needs to be an integrated management model that can be applied to both operational and developmental projects within the organisation.

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